

Suppression of Residual Hydrophobicity of Amphiphilic Amino Acids by forming Association Complexes with β -Cyclodextrin

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The interfacial tension at the benzene/water interface has been studied in the presence of four amphiphilic amino acids, viz. alanine, phenylalanine, valine and leucine in presence and in absence of β -cyclodextrin. The interfacial tension which is otherwise decreased with the increased concentration of amino acids, was found to increase gradually with progressive addition of cyclodextrin. The results have been explained on the basis of inclusion complexation between the hydrocarbon side-chain of the amino acid and cyclodextrin. The formation constants and other thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated for the inclusion complexes. It has been concluded that long and straight hydrocarbon side-chains are preferably included into the cavity of cyclodextrin molecule.

Some amino acids are amphiphilic in nature because they contain hydrocarbon side-chains linked with the amino acid backbone. Depending on the size and shape of these hydrocarbon side-chains, these amphiphilic amino acids exhibit aggregation and interfacial behaviour in the same way as those of surfactant molecule. As a matter of fact, the amphiphilic behaviour of these amino acids is believed to be responsible for different tertiary protein structures and it serves as an index of the protein localisation and function *in vivo*¹. If the hydrocarbon side-chains of these amino acids are somehow kept isolated from the surrounding water medium keeping rest part of the molecule in contact with aqueous solution, the aggregational and interfacial properties of these amphiphilic amino acids would be drastically altered. Cyclodextrins are bucket type of molecule of which the outer surface of the cavity is hydrophilic in nature while at the inside it is sufficiently hydrophobic. As a result, cyclodextrin forms adduct with organic compounds² of which the hydrophobic part of the guest molecule interacts with the inner cavity of the cyclodextrin to form an association complex through hydrophobic interaction. The molecule, in this way, keeps the hydrocarbon side-chain isolated from the direct contact with water.

This idea has been applied here whereby the hydrocarbon side-chain of the amino acid can be capped by the cyclodextrin molecule. When the hydrocarbon part of the amino acid molecule is intruded into the cavity, the complex no longer remains as amphiphile and the interfacial property as exhibited by uncomplexed amino acid is drastically reduced in the inclusion complexes.

Concentration-dependent interfacial tension is one of the suitable methods by which the amphiphilic nature of a molecule is ascertained³. Several workers measured the interfacial tension of the solution of various amino acids and calculated the relative hydrophobicities of these amino acid side-chains⁴. It is related to the free energy of transfer of these amino acids from the bulk of the solution to the interface. Data on the inclusion complexes of amino acid-cyclodextrin are available in the literature⁵. But no study

has yet been reported on how the interfacial and aggregational behaviour of these amphiphilic amino acids can be modulated by capping the hydrocarbon side-chains and thereby isolating them from the direct contact with water. Here, we report the interaction of some amphiphilic amino acid like leucine, valine, alanine and phenylalanine with β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions and the change of interfacial tension at benzene/water interface in the presence of these inclusion complexes. Since β -cyclodextrin has an intermediate cavity size compared to α - and β -cyclodextrins⁶, we have selected to use this compound in the present study.

Results and Discussion

A representative plot of the interfacial tension at the benzene/water interface as a function of amino acid concentration is shown in the Fig. 1 for valine. The results show that the interfacial tension decreases with the increase of the concentration of amino acid. Unfortunately the interfacial tension measurement can not be used to determine the CMC of the amphiphilic amino acid because the ex-

Fig. 1. Interfacial tension (γ) of water-benzene interface in presence of different concentrations of valine at (O) 25, (□) 35 and (Δ) 45.

trapolated CMC is higher than the solubility of amino acid in water. It is of some interest to note that the amphiphilic amino acid with longer hydrocarbon side-chain can decrease the interfacial tension more rapidly than that of shorter hydrocarbon side-chain. The decrease of interfacial tension is due to the accumulation of amino acid at the water/benzene interface. Because of the amphiphilic nature of these amino acids, these molecules are accumulated at the interface with hydrocarbon chain pointing towards benzene layer while the polar group are directed towards bulk water⁵.

Upon the addition of increasing amount of β -cyclodextrin to a known concentration of amino acid solution, the interfacial tension increases. The concentration of amino acid was not kept very large in comparison to β -cyclodextrin because they form 1 : 1 complex⁵. The molar ratio of β -cyclodextrin to the amino acid was represented by R . The change of interfacial tension of a fixed concentration of amino acid with progressive addition of β -cyclodextrin is shown in the Fig. 2 for leucine, valine, alanine and phenylalanine. The aqueous solution of β -cyclodextrin does not show any surface activity⁶. The interfacial tension is increased maximum in the case of phenylalanine and minimum for alanine. The above results may be explained in the following way. When β -cyclodextrin is added to the solution of amino acid, the amino acid otherwise adsorbed at the interface, undergoes complex formation. The inclusion complex of amino acid has no surface activity and the observed interfacial tension of amino acid + β -cyclodextrin system is attributed to be due to unreacted monomeric amino acid adsorbed at the interface⁶.

Inclusional association of ionic detergent molecules in

Fig. 2. Interfacial tension (γ) of water-benzene interface in presence of mixture of amino acid and β -cyclodextrin at different ratios ($R = [\beta\text{-CD}]/[\text{Amino acid}]$) at 25° : (□) alanine; (●) phenylalanine; (Δ) valine and (○) leucine.

the cavity of α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin has been observed⁷ in which the authors have attributed the association constant values for the inclusion process of cyclodextrin with detergent molecules to the differences of the hydrophobicities of the surfactant molecule. This idea has been applied in the study of association constant (K) of β -cyclodextrin + amino acid system. Since only one molecule of amino acid associates with one molecule of cyclodextrin⁵, the equilibrium reaction may be represented as

in which A represents amino acid and CD is cyclodextrin molecule. The association constant (K) of the reaction is represented by

$$K = \frac{[ACD]}{[A]_f [CD]_f} \quad (2)$$

where, $[ACD]$ is the concentration of cyclodextrin complex, $[A]_f$ and $[CD]_f$ are the concentrations of free amino acid and cyclodextrin in the equilibrium mixture respectively. If $[A]_0$ is the original concentration of amino acid, then $[ACD] = [A]_0 - [A]_f$. Similarly, if $[CD]_0$ is the original concentration of cyclodextrin, then

$$\begin{aligned} [CD]_f &= [CD]_0 - [ACD] \\ &= [CD]_0 - [A]_0 + [A]_f \end{aligned}$$

Putting all the values in equation (2), one can have

$$K = \frac{[A]_0 - [A]_f}{[A]_f \{ [CD]_0 - [A]_0 + [A]_f \}} \quad (3)$$

From the equation (2) it is clear that if $[A]_f$ is known, K can be easily evaluated. As we have found during the course of experiment that the interfacial tension of amino acid solution is increased in the presence of β -cyclodextrin and this is attributed to the fact that the hydrophobic moiety, the hydrocarbon chain of amino acid, is capped by β -cyclodextrin and the capped amino acid becomes nonsurface active entity. Under these circumstances the observed interfacial tension is a direct measure of the free uncomplexed amino acid which is left in the solution⁶. From concentration-dependence interfacial tension curve, the concentration of free uncomplexed amino acid, $[A]_f$ has been found out.

The K values for amino acids in the presence of β -cyclodextrin are shown in the Table 1. From the results it is apparent that K increases in the following order : alanine < phenylalanine < valine < leucine. Since leucine has highest binding constant with β -cyclodextrin, it be presumed that it has highest hydrophobicity among the four amino acids. Because of the shortest hydrocarbon side-chain (CH_3), alanine has minimum binding constant value. The increase in K values is also attributed to the stabilisation of inclusion compounds by the increase in the contact area

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS (K) OF AMINO ACID-CYCLODEXTRIN COMPLEX IN WATER AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Temp.	Leucine (M^{-1})	Valine (M^{-1})	Phenylalanine (M^{-1})	Alanine (M^{-1})
25	18.51	11.66	11.30	9.77
35	39.10	34.09	28.05	26.30
45	102.04	74.70	55.03	51.52

between the hydrocarbon side-chain of amino acid and the inner wall of the cyclodextrin molecule⁷. The binding constant of the inclusion complexes has been measured at different temperatures (Table 1). The results reveal that with the increase of temperature, K value increases tremendously. An analysis of the data shows that although leucine and valine contain same terminal isopropyl group in the hydrocarbon side-chain, the association constant of valine is lower than that of leucine because the longer chain of leucine makes more favourable interaction for the hydrophobic inclusion process. Longer hydrocarbon chain preferably forms stronger inclusion complex. Studies of the structure of the cyclodextrin hexahydrates have shown that in the crystal form of the compound, two water molecules are located inside the cavity which are of hydrogen bonded to each other⁸. The molecule in this form is in a tense conformation and is less symmetrical. When a hydrophobic moiety is fixed into the cavity, it is possible that the hydrated water molecule inside the cavity are replaced and the molecule is released of its tense conformation⁹.

Recently much attention has been paid on the elucidation of the driving force leading to the complexation between cyclodextrin and a guest molecule and the understanding of the inclusion mechanism is mostly attained based on the molecular thermodynamics. There are several kinds of interactions between the cyclodextrin and a guest molecule given by the following equation⁷,

$$\Delta G = \Delta G_{hp} + \Delta G_{polar} + \Delta G_{ster} + \Delta G_{hb} + \Delta G_{tors} + \Delta G_{rel}$$

where ΔG_{hp} , ΔG_{polar} , ΔG_{ster} , ΔG_{hb} , ΔG_{tors} and ΔG_{rel} are the free energy changes attributed to the hydrophobic interaction, polar interaction, steric interaction, hydrogen bonding, torsional energy and the release of the water molecule with high energy respectively. Among these interactions, the hydrophobic interaction and the Van der Waals interaction might be mainly contributing to the thermodynamic parameters.

The change of the free energy of the inclusion process has been calculated from the association constant (K) as

$$\Delta G^\circ = -2.303 R T \log K \quad (4)$$

where the free energy change ΔG° is given by the equation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (5)$$

The enthalpy change accompanying the complex formation can be determined from the values of binding constant at different temperatures using the integrated form of Vant

Hof equation,

$$\log K = \frac{-\Delta H}{2.3 RT} + \text{constant} \quad (6)$$

Once the values of ΔG° and ΔH° are known, ΔS° can be calculated from equation (5). The calculated values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS of the β -cyclodextrin + amino acid system are shown in Table 2. It is seen that ΔH is negative and ΔS is positive and $T\Delta S \gg \Delta H$. Negative ΔH indicates that inclusion process is exothermic for all the four amino acids used. It may be attributed to the Van der Waals interaction, i.e. hydrophobic interaction between the inner wall of the cyclodextrin molecule and the hydrocarbon chain of the amino acid⁷. The small value of ΔS is really surprising but could be explained from the compensatory effects between the inclusion process (negative ΔS) and the release of water molecules (positive ΔS) from the cavity of cyclodextrin during inclusion process⁷.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF AMINO ACID-CYCLODEXTRIN COMPLEXES

Substrate	$K(M^{-1})$	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Leucine	18.51	-7.233	-0.638 3	22.13
Valine	11.66	-6.087	-0.699 038	18.08
Phenylalanine	11.30	-6.01	-0.614 005	18.09
Alanine	9.77	-5.649	-0.617 45	16.83

*At 25°.

Conclusion : The amphiphilicity of some of amino acids, like leucine, valine, phenylalanine and alanine has been investigated from the interfacial tension measurements at the benzene/water interface and it has been found that the amphiphilic character of these amino acids can be considerably suppressed by adding β -cyclodextrin into the aqueous solutions of these amino acids. Cyclodextrin has been found to form inclusion complexes with these amino acids in which it has been presumed that the hydrocarbon side-chains are inserted into the inner cavity of cyclodextrin molecule. Since the outer peripheral surface of the cyclodextrin is hydrophilic, the inclusion complex renders minimum contact between the hydrocarbon side-chain and water. As a result, the amphiphilic property of the amino acid is drastically suppressed.

Experimental

β -Cyclodextrin (Fluka; 99% pure) and different amino acids (A.R. grade; 99% pure, Sigma) were used as such. Double-distilled water was used.

Interfacial tension was measured at 25–45° employing the drop-volume method using a stalagnometer, and the equilibrium drop was obtained within 1–2 min. The procedure is to form drops at the end of capillary and allowing them to fall into a container until enough have been collected, so that the volume of one drop can be determined

accurately. The interfacial tension (γ) was evaluated from the relation,

$$\gamma = \frac{v(\rho_w - \rho_o) g}{2 \pi r f} \quad (7)$$

where, v is the volume of one drop of the aqueous solution, ρ_w the density of water, ρ_o the density of oil and f the correction factor which depends on the radius of the tip and the volume of one drop. Standard deviation is ± 0.2 . The interfacial tension was measured at pH 7.0 and in 0.1 M KNO_3 solution.

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